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Pastoral Counselling and Family Stability

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Abstract

Pastoral counseling simply means a kind of therapy that integrates psychological principles with spiritual guidance and pastoral care, which is often provided by clergy members or trained professionals within a religious context. This is very vital in every facet of human endeavour in the society, especially at the family level. The complexity of the composition of humanity emanates from the family units and the world view of any society is built upon the acceptable and approved norms which are foremost preserved and practiced at the family level which automatically permeate every nook and cranny of the society. However, problem ensued in the family with various forms of instabilities as a result of the demonical forces which have infiltrated and disrupted the ranks and files of the world order, a reflection of which was recorded in Genesis 6: 1-6, hence, this necessitated the Divine, the Supreme Being, who created a secured world to be raising his servants, the prophets, pastors, etc, to offer counsel to humanity, and the strategy that God maps out at times is to offer counsel to the family because once stability is enhanced in the family, it will permeate other aspect of human endeavours. Using sociological and historical methods to gather relevant information, sociologically, interview was conducted with fifty families who are well advanced in marriage and the data collated and analysed using simple percentage method, and from the result, it is unequivocally evident that pastors are undaunted to offer the right counsels that will enhance family stability in the face of heinous crimes bedeviling our family, causing instability, confusion and insecurity.

Key Words: Pastoral, Counselling, Family,

Pastoral Counselling

Pastoral Counseling: "Pastoral counseling is the practice of talking with individuals, couples, and families to increase their understanding of emotional and religious conflicts and to help resolve problems using religious and other resources" (Moruf, 2023). Also, "Pastoral counseling is a form of counseling that integrates psychological principles with spiritual guidance, often provided by clergy or individuals with a strong religious background" (Moruf, 2023), or "Pastoral counseling is a form of counseling that integrates psychological insights with spiritual guidance, often provided by religious leaders or trained professionals within a faith community" (Moruf, 2023) and this counseling is usually provided by clergy or trained individuals in order to address spiritual, emotional or psychological issues of life that relate to individuals, families or the society at large.

Each family is a composite part of the larger society and seeks to exist and survive in a pluralistic society of which many people, irrespective of their arrogant and uncompassionate social relationships among humanity still claim to have a worthwhile religious way of life, what

a paradox! Donald Bloesch rightly said that they are “arrogant and uncompassionate in a world of pluralism, a world in which there are many worthwhile religious ways” (Donald, 1991) and when a family lives in a society full of such personalities, pastoral guidance will be required so as not to fall victim of their intricacies, because when a member of any family is in a dilemma among such people, the kind of therapy such people will proffer, most often will not achieve the desired result, beside, there is a limit and extent to which any therapy can take care of, Richard has this to say: “However intricately a clinical theory can help us analyze a client’s dilemma, it cannot tell us why any of the various dramas in anyone’s life is worth caring about or what meaning our lives have --- We can do therapy, come up with clever interventions, but we’re going to die anyway, just like everybody else” (1991)

Hence, the need for the involvement of pastoral counselling of which mature spirituality often times comes into play or use, whereby various potentialities and factors are applied so as to proffer lasting solution to any unsatisfactory situation or circumstance. Scott Peck, in explaining mature spirituality, as a yardstick of proffering solution to a deplorable situation and a state of dilemma in a family and the society at large, through unity with one another and with the universe, has this to say, “a mystical communal stage of spiritual development, a stage of unity, of an underlying connectedness between things: between men and women, between us and the other creatures and even inanimate matter as well, fitting together according to an ordinarily invisible fabric underlying the cosmos” (Scott, 1987).

Family, according to Advanced English Dictionary, “is a social group or unit that live together, consisting of parents and their children” (Advanced English Dictionary, 2023), is not isolated from the troubles of the world, a nuclear family which consists of the father and mother and their children ought to be a place of consistent happiness and joy together with everything that makes life merry, but alas, it has not always been so. The kind of challenge some families pass through often presents to the world that there are unseen forces wagging war against the family. Andrian Rogers rightly said that, “but today all of the artillery of hell seems to be aimed at the nuclear family- humanism, relativism, materialism, hedonism” (Adrian, 2005). When pondering on the various ills that bedevil families, Garry Collins, in his book, *Family Shock: Keeping Families Strong in the Midst of Earthshaking change* has this to say;

“--- many people today are scared, fearful about their safety, worried about their families, and lacking in hope for the future. Almost every day the newspapers and television reporters tell us about crime, abuse, uncontrolled sexuality, militant groups that push their perverted values, teenage pregnancies, poverty – stricken families, single – parent frustrations, poor schools, neglected children, and kids that kill other kids. In our homes – including the homes of Christians –there is conflict, tension, insensitivity, communication breakdown, and probably more abuse than we dare admit. We face endless demands that rob us of our time, pull us apart, and disrupt our hopes for family unity and stability. A host of forces shake our homes and cause our families to crumble, but three are of major impact: catastrophic change, persistent pressure, and pervasive pessimism” (1995).

However, of all the predicaments that befall the family, there is a potent weapon with which they could be addressed or taken care of, and as regard this, Rogers says, “The chief weapon in our arsenal is truth that brings a fixed standard for right and wrong, and that truth is

encapsulated in the ten commandments” (2005). This emphatically shows that pastoral counseling is required in each family so as to curtail, curb, and check the various menaces therein. God is interested in the well-being of the family, even from the record about the first family that God created in the Bible, in Genesis chapter 3, the cordial relationship of visiting the couple in the cool of the day which God established between himself and the first family indicates that God is concerned for their wellness. Rogers added that, “God has a plan to give us successful homes. It is given to us in his Word and is communicated in divine shorthand in the Ten Commandments. His perfect law. If we want to have homes that win, we can rediscover God’s will as revealed in His Ten Commandments” (2005). According to Plato, “The life of the nation is the life of the family written large”, and if there will not be solid cohesion and national security in a nation, it is from the family such foundation is easily laid, just as Adrian opined, “There is a war going on ---, a battle for the soul of our nation. The battleground is the home, and *the issue is truth*, Satan has aimed all of the artillery of hell at our homes, and every shell in that artillery is a lie” (2005). Hence pastoral counselling is of necessity so as to help evade these intricacies and to manoeuvre all the manipulations of Satan against the family. Various aspects of the family that possibly require the counselling of a pastor are discussed below:

Marital Problems

The many challenges or conflicts witnessed in a marriage are symptoms of attitudes such as lack of love, anger, selfishness, unwillingness to forgive, bitterness, anxiety, communication gap or problems, sexual mistreatment, substance abuse, sin, feeling of inferiority, deliberate rejection of God’s will, etc, and according to Collins, “each of these can cause tension in the home, each can be influenced by husband or wife” (Gary, 2007). Scripturally, Gary asserts that, marital problems, per se, are not analysed, but affirms that, the Scriptures deal with marital conflict only indirectly and in passing, the issues underlying many marriage problems are considered in detail (Gary, 2007). The major three categories of marital problems are unfulfilled expectations, disappointing sex, and faulty communication. Pastors need to come in to offer useful counsel of the probable way forward or out of such situations based on the Scriptural directives, Holy Spirit, experiences, etc.

As regard unfulfilled expectations, some couples experience variations in their marital expectations which could be complex or simple. These expectations, for instance, range from how to spend their weekends, how best to celebrate their birthdays, how they intend spending their money and how they would have wanted the various duties at home to be discharged, and amazingly, problem of frustrations from time to time sets in, when variations such as the above are ignored, and such problems might be difficult to handle.

Concerning disappointing sex, couples are shaped on the background of their cultural worldview, especially from the knowledge acquired from experienced old couples on teachings about their sex lives. This orientation shaped their mentality which culminates into what individual spouse would expect in their marital sexual lives, some might have hope of exciting and consistently satisfying sex lives, while some might be nursing fears and uncertainties in marital sex.

Also, about faulty communication, whenever communication, either verbal or non-verbal, which is expected to involve sending and receiving of message, results in contradiction, it can lead to confusion and communication breakdown. A person facial outlook or countenance ought to tally with the verbal expression, a person's action should agree with his verbal expressions.

Other issues that can cause marital problems are;

Unhealthy relationships, whereby a partner in a marriage gets close and builds intimacy with another person, such might be suspicious, and might betray trust, which can make the husband and wife to drift apart and as such, stops sharing confidence, stop developing life goals together which might make any of them to be vulnerable.

Unwise choice, the choice a spouse makes in a marriage that might make or mar the marriage, wrong choices can crumble a marriage. Keeping secrets is also an important issue that can cause marital problems. Likewise, a weakening emotional bond can cause marital problems, the emotional bond between a husband and wife has been called the "golden thread that holds partner together" (Frank, 1987). Boredom can also cause marital problems, a situation when a marriage is dull and routine, which might make couples to look somewhere else for variety. Personal differences, etc can cause family problems.

Pastoral Counseling in Marital Problems

Involving in pastoral counseling is highly tasky, Gary wrote, "This is the kind of work that demands a lot of prayers and reliance on the Holy Spirit. Before starting, (and frequently thereafter) counselors should look at themselves to clarify some of their own attitudes, possible prejudices, motivations and vulnerabilities" (Gary, 2007). The following should be considered in pastoral counseling;

The counselor, firstly, should take a close look at himself, together with his attitudes and biases. Also, the counselor should be alert to special issues that relate to couples counseling. Likewise, the counselor should try to determine the reason the couple has come for counseling. More so, the counselor should not lord it over the couple, rather, he should partner with them in setting of goals.

Furthermore, the counselor should focus on the person, not himself, he should also focus on the problems, he should also focus on the process, and he should be conscious of common mistakes and try to avoid making them. When a couple is well guided pastorally, a good marriage is built up that give birth a healthy family, hence a coherent and secured society at large.

Family Problems

"No family is perfect and without problems and periodic crises" (Collins, 1995) and the problems that bedevil families range from misunderstanding that culminates into crisis, conflicts, there are communication breakdown, insensitivity, tension, unmet desire and demand, unrest among kids, poverty, abuse of various kinds, etc, as opined earlier, "--- A host of forces shake our homes and cause our families to crumble, but three are of major impact: catastrophic change, persistent pressure, and pervasive pessimism" (Gary, 1995), and in the face of all these challenges and difficulties, how each family responds differs, because "Every family

is unique. This impacts how they cope with problems and how they can be helped. For example, there are several influences that mold every family and create family distinctive" (Gary, 1995). Also, the factors that cause these problems in families range from one family to another, such as; issue of personal history, of which secrets are kept without revealing it to other members of the family, like divorce or previous marriage, illegitimate pregnancy, past affair with other people, etc and all these can hinder people from coping honestly during crisis in a family when eventually known. Also, issue of stress whereby a member of the family is stressed up and finds it difficult to relate with others well at a given point in time, likewise, issue of resources, where some families can cope well due to strength and skills acquired by members of the family while on the other hand, there might be breakdown of peace due to certain weakness in some members of the family. Other issues are also critical such as communication style to be adopted in the family, worldview, rules to be observed, values that are cherished, intimacy, role clarity, commitment to agreement, (Gary, 2007) etc.

Pastoral Counseling and the Family

The various family problems which are discussed above will necessitate the involvement of pastoral counseling so as to offer counsel or guidance of the probable way forward. However, when pastoral guidance are to be proffered or given in a family, the cognizance of the following should be taken; immediate practical guidance should be given, focus should be concentrated on the family and not individual, attempt in analyzing the present should be the priority and not the past, psychological approach should be adopted so as to reduce family tension, referring the family to where more help or solution could be accessed, and when families are helped to resolve crisis will definitely and eventually give the family the wherewithal to handle their problems from time to time (Gary, 2007).

Conclusion

Pastors are strategically positioned to offer or proffer guidance and advice leading to probable solution to various problems, challenges, crisis, and most often, the pastors are spiritually inclined and influenced to give illumination to the dark situation by using the Scripture, experience and the leading of the Holy Spirit. Since each family is a composite unit of the larger society that causes varying degree of problems to the family, then, each family should avail herself of the availability of Pastors who will offer spiritual guidance.

Recommendations

The following are the probable recommendations:

1. Each family should have a spiritual father who serves as the family pastor so as to offer useful counsel during troubles and challenges
2. Family altar where they worship together, study the word of God and teach the word of God to their subjects should be encouraged.
3. Pastors should not relent in heralding how marriages and homes should conduct themselves in noble practices.

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4. Pastors should encourage NGOs and other governmental agencies to sensitize the public about right and wrong values of life, and they should desist from all forms of assaults.
 5. Churches and communities should have welfare units and centers that are composed of pastors where families with difficulties can be directed to for guidance

Appendix

Some of the questions during the interview:

1. What has been the cause of instability in the family?
2. Which role does the father or mother or children play during instability in the family?
3. Is God needed during instability in the family?
4. Mention some of the challenges encountered during instability in the family
5. Can peace be sustained in the family?
6. What should the father, mother and the children do so as to check instability in the family?

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